

ANALISIS MAHASISWA PROGRAM STUDI PENDIDIKAN GEOGRAFI DALAM PERSPEKTIF SPASIAL SEBAGAI UPAYA PENJARINGAN MAHASISWA BARU

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan untuk mengetahui profil dan menganalisis persebaran spasial mahasiswa Program Studi Pendidikan Geografi angkatan 2016-2019. Metode penelitian yang digunakan adalah deskriptif. Bentuk penelitian survei dengan responden sebanyak 196. Teknik pengambilan data menggunakan komunikasi tidak langsung, alat yang digunakan adalah angket. Data yang digunakan yaitu nama, asal, agama, jenis kelamin, pendidikan terakhir, pekerjaan, dan pendapatan orang tua. Teknik pengambilan sampel dengan *stratified sampling*. Teknik analisis data menggunakan deskriptif kuantitatif dan persentase. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan mahasiswa Program Studi Pendidikan Geografi paling banyak beragama Islam 95 orang; berjenis kelamin wanita 144 orang; pendidikan dari SMA Jurusan IPS 166 orang; pekerjaan orang tua petani 96 orang; penghasilan rata-rata orang tua Rp760.000,00/bulan; informasi tentang Program Studi Pendidikan Geografi paling banyak didapatkan dari saudara sebanyak 74 orang; motivasi masuk karena berkeinginan untuk mengetahui seluk beluk bumi sebanyak 64 orang. Persebaran mahasiswa Program Studi Pendidikan Geografi menunjukkan pola distribusi yang menyebar.

Kata Kunci: analisis mahasiswa program studi; penjarangan mahasiswa baru; perspektif spasial.

Abstract

This research aimed to determine the profile and analyze the spatial distribution of students from the 2016-2019 Geography Education Study Program. The research method used descriptive. The form of the survey with 196 respondents. The data collection technique used indirect communication, the tool used is a questionnaire. The data used name, origin, religion, gender, last education, occupation, and parents' income. The sampling technique used stratified sampling. The data analysis technique used descriptive quantitative and percentage. The results showed that the most students of the Geography Education Study Program were 95 Muslims; female sex 144 people; education from SMA majoring in Social Sciences 166 people; the occupation of the farmer's parents were 96 people; the average income of parents was Rp.760,000.00/month; Information about the Geography Education Study Program was mostly obtained from relatives as many as 74 people; The motivation to enter was because they want to know the ins and outs of the earth 64 people. The distribution of students from the Geography Education Study Program showed a distributed distribution pattern.

Keywords: analysis of study program students; new student screening; spatial perspective.

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